

ISic3148

I.Sicily inscription 3148

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Gela

Place of origin (modern)

Gela

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Gela, Museo Archeologico

Regionale di Gela

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI329695

1. Λεύκο̅ν Χαίρε̅σίλεο̅ι.

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645489

EDCS 64800158

PHI 329695

Bibliography

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Orsi, P. 1900. Frammenti epigrafici sicelioti. *Rivista di storia antica*. 5: 39-66. At 50 no.19

Arena, R. 2002. Iscrizioni greche arcaiche di Sicilia e Magna Grecia. Iscrizioni di Sicilia. II. Iscrizioni di Gela e di Agrigento. Alessandria. At no.63

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